

Deliverable 11.1

Provider adoption and evaluation report of Year 2 blueprint and technology, including barriers to adoption & EOSC readiness of the TRE providers with recommendations

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1. Executive Summary

The EOSC-ENTRUST project works on the development and integration of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This report outlines the work done during the second project year in the Providers work package (WP11).

Between M13–M24, WP11's key achievements include the second TRE inventory (MS10), the development of the requirements management framework, the launch of the Open TRE Provider Forum (OTPF), and a Blueprint adoption and EOSC-readiness analysis, drawing out recommendations to support adoption efforts and EOSC integration. WP11 conducted this work through biweekly meetings in which information gathering and analysis was conducted and organised.

The updated TRE inventory is the first public version of this project output, capturing information on both EOSC-ENTRUST affiliated and non-affiliated TREs globally. The TRE inventory was updated to align with the TRE catalogue (D13.3) to address gaps and capture more complete information. Using a revised structure, the updated version of the inventory provides details of 25 TREs. The inventory outlines TRE capabilities in key categories, including access and accessibility, data types and security, computing and analytics services, and data discovery. The updated inventory supports the development of further project deliverables, including the TRE catalogue and the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, highlighting gaps to be addressed and potential barriers in the TRE landscape in Europe, such as differences in national policies and a varied landscape for reference architectures. The inventory findings also highlighted that TREs are often very flexible to suit the needs of projects involving sensitive data, within the limits of organisational or national policies. Much work also remains to be done for supporting federated queries.

The requirements management framework has added a further facet to WP11's outputs. The work done on this was based on the requirements outlined by WP8 in MS8. WP11 organised two workshops to support the development of this framework, addressing how to move from requirements to evidence and producing a Requirement Adoption Traceability Matrix. This matrix offers a theoretical model of how TRE requirements can be linked to types of evidence that validates them, thereby allowing TREs to be evaluated on their capabilities.

The Open TRE Provider Forum launched in April 2025 and held seven meetings before the end of M24, serving as a forum for all TRE service providers in Europe. The forum's membership rose to 45 individuals by the end of M24, with an average of 10 participants per meeting. The OTPF will continue to develop as a forum for TRE related news, updates, community discussion, and information sharing. The OTPF promotes interoperability and will also highlight EOSC-ENTRUST results and deliverables until the end of the project.

WP11 furthermore conducted analysis on EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint adoption, as well as EOSC-readiness of TREs. WP11 providers have differing approaches to adopting the Blueprint, from alignment to using it to shape institutional TRE policy. Significant barriers remain, however, in providers' adoption of the Blueprint, which are analysed here. Linked to Blueprint adoption is TREs becoming a part of EOSC offerings, which remains an oblique question in the rapidly evolving EOSC landscape. Currently no EOSC nodes are able to process sensitive data, and TRE integration and onboarding onto EOSC nodes needs further development. To this end, this report provides recommendations and outlines support needed to bring TREs closer to EOSC integration.

The efforts captured in this report have benefited from collaboration with other EOSC-ENTRUST work packages, and in particular the Drivers and Architecture work packages. Through close collaboration, the Providers WP has been able to update the methodology for the TRE inventory, as well as ensure alignment with the TRE catalogue and conduct adoption analysis of the Blueprint. Collaboration across work packages has also benefited the requirements management framework, for which MS8 formed the basis of.

The work conducted M13–24 of the project has laid the groundwork for the final project year. Between M25–M36, as WP12, the Providers work package will focus on four different tasks. First, the TRE inventory will receive a third and final update, aiming to include as many TREs as possible. A second focus is drafting a sustainability model for the OTPF, which will explore how to run the forum beyond the EOSC-ENTRUST project itself. A third task is defining the role and possible entry points of TREs into the EOSC Federation, and the final point of focus will be a final assessment of Blueprint adoption.

The work presented in this deliverable forms the basis for a more unified and interoperable approach to sensitive data sharing in European research. At the end of the report, a discussion on next steps and impact on the European TRE landscape thus far are examined.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	Yes
	2. A ‘starter pack’ of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No

	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	Yes
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	No
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	Yes
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safe principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)	No
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes
Objective 3 National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes
	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	Yes
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No

<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.</p>	1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
	2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).	No
	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	Yes
	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9).	No

3. Introduction

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the work done by the EOSC-ENTRUST Providers work package (henceforth WP11) in its second year, outlining key achievements, challenges, and future directions. WP11 has focused on fostering a federated approach to TREs within Europe and within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative. These efforts are a response to a currently fragmented TRE landscape, which raises challenges of interoperability and limited ability to share sensitive data across boundaries, both national and disciplinary. Through TRE federation efforts, the project and WP11 seek to establish structures for increased interoperability, information sharing, and, where possible, standardisation amongst European TREs.

To achieve these aims, certain structures need to be in place. There needs to be an improved understanding of TRE requirements and capabilities to see which aspects are the most unified and mature, and which aspects in contrast are most fragmented and will need focused efforts to address. To this end WP11 has produced an updated TRE inventory (MS11)¹, which was published in M18 and captures the capabilities of 25 TREs across 15 countries. The inventory provides descriptions of TRE stakeholders, with certain caveats: the work of WP11 does not capture the goals, objectives, or responsibilities of TRE stakeholders, nor does it enable setting up rules of engagement needed to enable and promote collaboration and coexistence. These factors still require further work in the wider TRE landscape.

¹ Vihervalli, U. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST MS11: Updated TRE Inventory (1.0) [Data set]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960481>; Vihervalli, U., & Azab, A. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST MS11: Summary of Updated TRE capabilities. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960482>

WP11 has, however, made efforts in establishing a forum for TRE collaboration that enables knowledge exchange, community discussions, and the opportunity to share best practices. The Open TRE Provider Forum (OTPF) launched in M14 and is open to all TRE service providers regardless of the maturity of their TREs. This aims to bring European TRE service providers together, to facilitate information exchange, and to set up a community-led initiative that can also take ownership of EOSC-ENTRUST outputs such as the inventory and/or catalogue.

WP11 has also produced a requirements management framework. This framework manages and documents TRE requirements, providing an updated requirements list linked to evidence artifacts to enable validation. Through this work, led by BSC, WP11 has formulated a Requirement Adoption Traceability Matrix, which can provide feedback for the project's Drivers and for the Blueprint development work. The requirements compiled in MS8² served as the basis for this work.

The above efforts have informed the analysis of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint adoption and the assessment of EOSC-readiness. WP11 has conducted information gathering amongst service providers to see the range of Blueprint adoption at this stage, identify the forms and degrees of adoption, and what barriers remain against additional or complete adoption.

This also informs the analysis of EOSC-readiness: EOSC has evolved significantly since EOSC-ENTRUST launched in March 2024, with the EOSC Federation launching officially in November 2025. EOSC as a collection of federated nodes is quickly taking shape, with 13 national, infrastructure, and thematic nodes piloted in 2025, and the EOSC EU Node providing federating capabilities. At the time of writing, none of the existing nodes offer sensitive data analysis or have onboarded TREs. For WP11, the central question is in what way can TREs become a part of EOSC offerings and, further, what requirements does a TRE need to meet in order to integrate with EOSC. This report offers recommendations for support required in this regard. WP11 is also monitoring the development of European Health Data Space (EHDS) requirements to ensure alignment as these become more concrete.

This deliverable provides a description of the above work as follows: the updates to the TRE inventory, the requirements management framework, the Open TRE Provider Forum (OTPF), the analysis for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint adoption levels and the identification of barriers, and an analysis of EOSC integration with recommendations. After this, a conclusion, description of next steps, and an impact overview are provided.

By documenting these efforts, this report supports ongoing collaboration amongst TRE providers, as well as informing policymakers and other key stakeholders. The overall aim is the continued improvement in research accessibility and data security in the European research landscape. The work has been conducted through various methods, including biweekly WP11 meetings, monthly OTPF meetings, surveys, reporting, collaborative writing and other information gathering. Lastly, AI tools have been used in this report to generate tables and summary outlines; this content has been human-verified.

² van der Kant, A., Dang, S., Panagiotopoulou, M., Casado Barbero, M., Curwin, A. J., Tuikka, A.-M., Wiltshire, D., Bolton, S., & Lichtwardt, B. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST MS8 Revised Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers report. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17376746>

4. Description of work accomplished

This chapter is structured around the six key objectives of WP11:

- Updating and maintaining the TRE inventory
- Requirements management framework
- Open TRE Provider Forum
- Facilitating the adoption of the Blueprint and developed technologies
- Planning an overall approach for making TREs part of the EOSC offering
- Supporting the providers to onboard TREs to EOSC

4.1 Updating and maintaining the TRE inventory

4.1.1 Refining the TRE inventory

The first iteration of the TRE inventory (MS10³) was compiled through a survey for EOSC-ENTRUST partners and was published within the project in M6. The inventory captured structured information about TREs, such as requirements, operational details, and capabilities. MS10 was used to inform other work packages and their outputs, namely the Drivers and Architecture work packages.

As the survey was found to be a successful method for data gathering, the same approach was adopted for the second TRE survey, resulting in the second TRE inventory. The survey, however, needed revisions to match how it had been utilised for the TRE catalogue (D13.3⁴), as these two outputs are closely linked. The correlation between the TRE inventory and the TRE catalogue has been well-described by WP14 as follows: “the TRE Inventory is more aimed at getting an overview of the organisational landscape, whereas the TRE catalogue could also include more technical details. The Inventory should be maintained by the Provider Forum also after the project ending, whereas the TRE Provider Catalogue is intended to be part of the EOSC offering.”⁵

To ensure that the updated inventory remains aligned with the catalogue, the survey was reworked to match the catalogue structure. The first section asked respondents to provide organisational details and basic details of their TRE(s). The following sections addressed access and accessibility, data types and security, computing and analytics services provided, and reference architecture details.

The survey was open to all TRE providers, marking a different target group than its first version that was aimed at EOSC-ENTRUST partners solely. This required dissemination and marketing efforts from WP11, as well as collaboration with the Communications work package. WP11 targeted all who had done the first survey, asking these stakeholders to provide information for the updated inventory likewise. WP11 also aimed to reach new audiences, and for this social media and newsletters were used, including the EOSC newsletter, which has a broad readership. The survey ran for two months, from mid-May 2025 to mid-July 2025.

³ EOSC-ENTRUST MS10 - Inventory & Summary of Current TRE Capabilities (internal project access only): <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/10-6vWgMhO3E8yFp-4aslHOBYPHra4EsxM/edit?usp=sharing&oid=113837283938400493695&rtpof=true&sd=true>

⁴ Kallberg, M., Baxter, R., Kirschenmann, S., & Lehväslaiho, H. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.3 Machine-readable First Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14412490>

⁵ Kallberg, M., & Kirschenmann, S. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D14.2 Machine-readable Second Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17251348>, 9.

The dissemination efforts were successful as the survey had a higher response rate of 25 TREs, across 24 different host organisations. After the data had been gathered, WP11 separated the data into two categories: data that can be shared in a public inventory, and sensitive data that cannot be shared due to security risks. Any data deemed to be sensitive was removed from the public version of the inventory, but the raw data was made available to EOSC-ENTRUST partners. The end-result was the publication of the second TRE inventory at M18, accompanied by an analysis report that gives detailed discussion for each of the survey questions.

4.1.2 Commonalities in TRE capabilities as per updated inventory

The updated inventory captures consistencies across TRE providers, highlighting commonalities in current TRE capabilities. Of these, security and compliance were the most consistent, although what policy or legal basis providers needed to align with differed between providers. The ISO 27001 certificate remained as a key standard across the spectrum, with those without one recording that they were working towards it. The survey did not ask respondents to specify the security standard they were operating in, but some of the breadth across Europe is summarised by the following table (Table 1).

Country	Framework	Notes
EU	NIS 2	Strong link to ISO 27001
Netherlands	NEN 7510	Healthcare – strong link to ISO 27001
Netherlands	BIO/BIO2	Public sector, strong link to ISO 27001
Germany	B3S “Branchenspezifischer Sicherheitsstandard – Medizinische Versorgung”	For hospitals, built on ISO 27001 and ISO 27799
	BSI C5 “Cloud Computing Compliance Criteria Catalogue”	For commercial cloud providers that handle health related data. While ISO 27001 is a framework for establishment and operation of an Information Security Management System (ISMS), BSI C5 defines required measures, prescribed and audited processes and controls.
France	HDS (“Hébergement de Données de Santé”)	Mandatory certification for health-data hosting, requiring an ISO 27001-certified ISMS
Spain	ENS (“Esquema Nacional de Seguridad”)	Mandatory for public-sector systems and their providers, with an official mapping to ISO 27001:2022
Belgium	eHealth “Minimale Normen	For healthcare IT, inspired by ISO 27000

	(MNM) & Implementatierichtlijnen”	series, and NIS2 implementation giving presumption of conformity for ISO 27001-certified essential entities (including many health actors)
Denmark	ISO 27001 adopted as the state security standard	Mandatory for all state authorities since 2014 and contractually binding for regions (public hospitals) through the Joint Regional Information Security Policy
Sweden	National Board of Health and Welfare regulation on information management and EHRs	Requires use of security standards, “at the moment SS-ISO/IEC 27001:2006,” in health institutions

Table 1. European security frameworks, produced by AI tools, human-checked.

It must be observed that some if not all TRE providers might be required to become NIS2 certified⁶; if not directly by law then by customers, data holders, or users who themselves must be NIS2 compliant. However, imposing hard requirements on TRE environment operators may exclude many academic infrastructures if mandatory certifications are expected, so it is essential to balance data security and integrity requirements against other requirements like availability, where the latter may not be as critical in academic or research environments. Security standards adhered to, thereby, while shown as essential to TRE providers, also encompass a variety of standards and needs, and further certifications may be required in the future.

The updated TRE inventory also showed that project area isolation was nearly universal across TREs, typically implemented through firewalls and network segmentation, underscoring a common commitment to safeguarding sensitive data. TREs also showed a broad range of support for tooling; while there are preferences for certain tools, researchers need and explore new toolings on a substantial scale to support their work.

Further commonalities in TRE capabilities were a preference for private or on-premise cloud solutions, reflecting that control and security are seen as essential requirements. However, this may pose a challenge for scalability in the future. At scale, private and on-premise clouds are often too limiting in terms of collaboration and compute/storage availability, as well as costly since they require a combination of capital expenditure and operating expenditure. Public-based service providers can, on the other hand, work fully on operating expenditures. At scale, the amount of small virtual machines needed on demand is often underestimated, and there is a long tail of specialised high compute in a pay-per-use setting.⁷ IT departments often underestimate the implications of having an on-premises cloud in a research setting when it is intended to be used at scale: cost, expertise, capacity (human and hardware), and security all need to be taken into account. Cloud solutions, therefore, should be monitored as TREs continue to develop.

⁶ Directive (EU) 2022/2555 (NIS2): <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2555/oj/eng>

⁷ See, for example, breakdown on costs at <https://insights.andrea-cloud.com/>

The TRE inventory further highlighted a preference for Linux-based operating systems, although Windows was also a common choice. This may be driven by a need for higher end virtual machines, although Windows can also be used for this end. While a preference for Linux in the overall landscape is discernible, operating systems also showed that one size rarely fits all, and that researchers have varied requirements. Many TREs also supported high-performance computing for imaging and machine learning, although the survey did not capture details of how these have been set up. There are indications that some do machine learning directly on their virtual machines, some use cloud services like Azure Machine learning, and some use APIs.

A final commonality demonstrated by the updated TRE inventory centres around data handling. TREs generally accept a broad range of data types for export and for use inside the environment, including common formats like spreadsheets and source code. Most TREs also allow unrestricted import types. Security checks are varied, with both manual and automated checks conducted, but each TRE has this process clearly defined. Additionally, the vast majority of TREs support public dataset discovery services, promoting transparency and enabling researchers to identify relevant resources easily.

4.1.3 Gap analysis based on updated TRE inventory

The updated TRE inventory also highlighted significant gaps in the TRE landscape, which impact the goals of EOSC-ENTRUST. A low level of federation readiness, which other project deliverables have also perceived,⁸ was further demonstrated by the inventory. This indicates that TREs have not considered federation to be a priority, or even something to strive towards; rather they have conceptualised their TRE as a non-federated environment. Support for federated queries is limited, underlining that many TREs cannot facilitate cross-TRE collaboration. This gap will require EOSC-ENTRUST to develop strategies to bridge these limitations, especially on how to work with policy-level dead-ends where national law or institutional policies form an obstacle to federation.

Another challenge lies in terminological and functional diversity. TREs are conceptualised in different ways and are often not documented in detail. Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) are not a direct equivalent of TREs but they have a legal basis in the EU through EHDS and the Data Governance Act (DGA).⁹ There are differences in GDPR roles and in the role of the service provider organisation, which are often not made explicit nor referenced in relation to established frameworks like Standard Contractual Clauses.¹⁰ Some TREs or SPEs might have non-fixed roles across their services. The more standardised and the more explicitly described these roles are, the easier and faster it is for TREs to come to a collaboration agreement. This highlights the need for a federation rulebook and common rules of engagement. While technology and related requirements change, a common governance and a federation rulebook is more stable and provides certainty and a basis for collaboration for all stakeholders.

⁸ Stansberg, C., Awan, H., Wolff, R., & Winge, I. (2026). EOSC-ENTRUST D14.4 Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year two Blueprint & Interoperability Framework, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299626>, 20: “European TREs are still at the very starting point when it comes to federation. Infrastructures are mature nationally but lack shared technical and legal frameworks for cross-border interoperability.”

⁹ For TRE-related terminology, see Lehväslaiho, H. (2025). SPE and TRE terminology for sensitive data processing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15696511>

¹⁰ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2021/91 on standard contractual clauses for the transfer of personal data: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec_impl/2021/914/oj

Reference architecture fragmentation adds another layer of complexity, but this may also benefit EOSC-ENTRUST. There is no dominant reference architecture in use, although SATRE arose as the most influential point of reference. Beyond this, TRE providers most often align themselves with institution-specific designs. TRE providers that provide their service at scale to multiple institutes, from a single PhD researcher to international multi-center studies, can provide evidence-based insights to address the challenges in interoperability. This, therefore, creates the opportunity for EOSC-ENTRUST to introduce a robust, internationally recognised Blueprint that can unify best practices, and which can be used for TREs to prepare themselves for EOSC and EHDS integration.

Finally, international accessibility constraints persist. While global collaboration is a discernible trend, many TREs still enforce national-only user registration and access. The biggest challenge for accessibility is the lack of an EU wide accepted legal framework – EU countries, as seen above, often implement their own version of mandatory certifications. While these are often based on ISO 27001, the variance between the certifications poses an obstacle, limiting the scalability of cross-border research initiatives. This requires adaptive solutions to navigate regulatory barriers. The positive is that progress is made in the academic world for creating blueprints for international multi-center collaboration. It is important that TREs support these blueprints.

4.2 Requirements management framework

A key contribution of WP11 has been the development of a Requirements Management (RM) framework to support good practices in the structured handling, evaluation and operationalisation of TRE requirements within EOSC-ENTRUST. The purpose of this framework is not to redefine project requirements, nor to set up compliance or enforcement mechanisms, but to provide a systematic and reproducible methodological instrument for the consistent analysis and verification of requirements adoption across a heterogeneous TRE provider landscape.

The RM framework establishes a common structure, terminology, and set of artefacts to support the full requirements lifecycle, from elicitation and analysis phases to baseline registration and change control. The framework has been formalised in a Requirements Management Plan (RMP)¹¹, presented as part of the presented report as a separate document. The RMP is explicitly designed to accommodate diversity in TRE architectures, governance models and maturity levels, as well as remain usable beyond the lifetime of the EOSC-ENTRUST project as a methodological reference.

The set of requirements collected and consolidated in MS8 were used as a practical use case to apply, validate and refine the RMP under real conditions. As part of this work, several requirement validation analyses were collaboratively carried out. To this end, WP11 organised the “EOSC-ENTRUST Workshop: From requirements to Evidence”¹², with the objective of assessing to what extent MS8 requirements could be evaluated through verifiable evidence, and how a structured traceability approach could support this evaluation. The following subsections summarise the RMP and details the workshop-derived analyses of MS8 requirements quality.

¹¹ Codó, L., Laine, H., & Kentros, Sotirios. (2026). EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Management Plan (v1.0). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18770711>

¹² EOSC-ENTRUST Workshop: From Requirements to Evidence: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1gZHav-0VjM7e65nyWCW3DagQ3y3DsgPnb1JIRw6xug/edit?usp=sharing>

4.2.1 Requirements Management Plan

The RMP provides the normative description of the requirements lifecycle processes, associated roles and responsibilities, governance model, adoption traceability procedures, and supporting artefacts. It emphasises low maintenance and sustainability-oriented design choices, alignment with international standards (notably ISO/IEC 29148), and reuse of existing community practices and open tooling. The RMP constitutes the reference document for the methodological approach applied.

The main components of the RM framework include:

- **EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Repository**

A public, version-controlled registry of the baseline requirements (*i.e.* MS8 requirements) and associated human-readable web catalogue that serves as the authoritative reference set for EOSC-ENTRUST requirements:

- Registry¹³
- Catalogue¹⁴

It contains:

- Structured requirement definitions (one JSON file per requirement) along with the model schemas and required code for requirement validation. The object model is aligned with ISO/IEC 29148 and compatible with ReqIF¹⁵ concepts, supporting versioning, traceability, and clarification.
- The online requirements catalogue is dynamically built from the registered requirements hosted at Github.
- Details on requirement change governance and workflow (*i.e.* [CONTRIBUTING.md](#), [CHANGELOG.md](#))

- **Requirement Adoption Traceability Matrix (RATM)**

A methodological tool implemented as a spreadsheet used to guide the linkage of requirements to potential evidence types. This includes controlled vocabularies for evidence types, roles, validation approaches, and maturity levels to enable consistent interpretation across providers.

- RATM Template¹⁶ (distributed as part of the Requirements Repository)
- Exemplary RATM application (mapping to evidence examples or suggestions)¹⁷

- **Governance guidance**

Lightweight guidance describing how requirements, evidence suggestions, and related

¹³ EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Repository Registry:
https://github.com/inab/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository

¹⁴ EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Repository Catalogue:
https://inab.github.io/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository/docs

¹⁵ ReqIF Format: <https://www.omg.org/reqif/>

¹⁶ EOSC-ENTRUST Requirement Adoption Traceability Matrix Template:
https://github.com/inab/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository/blob/main/templates/Requirement%20Adoption%20Traceability%20Matrix.xlsx

¹⁷ EOSC-ENTRUST Exemplary RATM application:
https://github.com/inab/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository/blob/main/ratm_example/Exemplary%20Requirement%20Adoption%20Traceability%20Matrix.xlsx

artefacts can be managed, updated, and reused over time with minimal operational overhead.

All components are designed to be open, reusable, and maintainable beyond the lifetime of the project, with the OTPF identified as a natural context for their continued use.

4.2.2 Analysis of MS8 requirements quality

The revised Driver requirements documented in MS8 were used to test the RM framework in practice. These requirements reflect genuine stakeholder needs and ambitions derived from real-world Drivers and therefore constitute a realistic and challenging input set. For the purposes of the requirements management framework development, MS8 requirements are considered the baseline requirements and have been registered in the EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Repository as the reference set for analysis.

During the application of the framework, it became evident that MS8 requirements were not yet “managed requirements” but “stakeholder requirements”, as they exhibit several structural characteristics that complicate evidence-based verifiability assessment, including:

- heterogeneous levels of granularity;
- varying degrees of technical specificity;
- overlaps and partial duplication;
- requirements expressed as principles, intents, or long-term aspirations rather than actionable statements;
- differing assumptions about responsibility (TRE-level, federation-level, or external actors).

Rather than treating these characteristics as deficiencies, the RMP explicitly accommodates them. It introduces a structured step for clarification, terminology harmonization, contextualization and scoping in the initial phases of the requirements lifecycle. Through this analysis, requirements were classified according to their Verifiability readiness (e.g. Verifiable, Partially Verifiable, not Verifiable), and importantly, “Clarification Notes” with assumptions or scope limitations (i.e. TRE-local, Federation-level, External actor) were recorded when necessary, always trying to preserve stakeholder intent.

This analysis provided valuable insight into how stakeholder-derived requirements behave when subjected to evidence-based evaluation and confirmed the relevance of a structured methodological approach.

4.2.3 Evidence-based assessment of MS8 requirements verifiability

The quality of clarified MS8 requirements was further analysed to assess how verifiable they are. During the workshop, participants collaboratively proposed examples of potential evidence artefacts, focusing on how different aspects of a requirement could be substantiated to demonstrate its adoption in practice.

By doing this exercise, the traceability procedures proposed in the RMP for standardising the process of producing, registering and validating evidence are put in practice for the first time. Evidence

suggestions were categorised using the controlled vocabularies and roles defined in the RMP, including:

- evidence type (e.g. governance, technical, operational, compliance);
- responsible actor (e.g. TRE operator, data protection officer, technical administrator);
- architecture specific (i.e. whether the evidence is architecture-dependent);
- expected validation or review approach (i.e. manual review, automatic review, etc.);
- indicative maturity level (i.e. policy, process, technical control, etc.)

The resulting set of evidence examples is intentionally illustrative and non-binding. As the result of a methodological exercise, its purpose is to demonstrate how requirements adoption can be evaluated in a structured and comparable way across providers, rather than to define mandatory artefacts or assessment criteria. For this reason, the consolidated evidence suggestions collected are not part of the RMP *per se*, but offered for guidance as part of the publicly available Requirements Repository, one of the RMP artifacts.

4.3 Open TRE Provider Forum

The Open TRE Provider Forum (OTPF) has been a major focus of WP11. The OTPF acts as a forum that is open for all TRE service providers in Europe. The aims of the OTPF are to 1) expand the Provider Forum with members that represent relevant organisations outside EOSC-ENTRUST, 2) disseminate information and results to the wider TRE provider community, 3) create a forum for TRE providers for knowledge exchange, peer support, and information sharing.

The OTPF launched in April 2025 and, by the time of publication of this report, has held seven meetings – five in 2025, and two in 2026. The OTPF is open to all TRE service providers in Europe, and initial marketing efforts were conducted via EOSC-ENTRUST communication channels as well as through WP11 networks.

The OTPF seeks to address the challenges of a fragmented TRE landscape in Europe, responding to interoperability issues and providing a forum for discussions on differing policy approaches. Members share information about their TREs and are able to raise questions and topics for community discussion, which seeks to create alignment and foster community led problem solving. The OTPF will also be used to highlight EOSC-ENTRUST results and deliverables until the end of the project, thus playing a key role in the dissemination of the project’s results.

The forum has seventeen founding member organisations from the EOSC-ENTRUST consortium who make up the Providers WP, some of which represent several TREs. These are:

Organisation	Country	Website
Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)	Spain	https://bsc.es/
Bielefeld University (de.NBI Cloud)	Germany	https://www.denbi.de/cloud
BIP4DAB – Associacao BIP4DAB	Portugal	https://biodata.pt/

CSC – IT Center for Science	Finland	https://csc.fi/
DeIC – Technical University of Denmark (DTU)	Denmark	https://www.deic.dk/
Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL)	Finland	https://thl.fi/
GRNET – National Infrastructures for Research and Technology	Greece	https://grnet.gr/
Health-RI	Netherlands	https://www.health-ri.nl/
IT4I@VSB – Technical University of Ostrava	Czechia	https://www.it4i.cz
Luxembourg National Data Service (LNDS)	Luxembourg	https://www.lnds.lu/
Sciensano	Belgium	https://www.sciensano.be
Sigma2 AS	Norway	https://www.sigma2.no/front-page
University of Dundee	United Kingdom	https://www.dundee.ac.uk/
University of Ljubljana	Slovenia	https://www.uni-lj.si/eng/
University of Tartu	Estonia	https://ut.ee/en
Uppsala University	Sweden	https://www.uu.se/en
Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie (VIB)	Belgium	https://vib.be/nl/home

Table 2. Provider forum core members from EOSC-ENTRUST project.

At the end of January 2026, the membership of the OTPF was 42 individuals, of whom 16 (38%) were non-EOSC-ENTRUST affiliated. WP11 will focus on raising that number in the final project year. In particular, one of the key goals of WP12 is to formulate a sustainability model for OTPF, enabling the forum to continue operations after EOSC-ENTRUST concludes.

The Provider forum thus operates at two levels: WP11 forms the core membership, meeting biweekly in sessions open for work package members. In these meetings, WP11's work is organised and conducted, including the planning of OTPF. The second level is the OTPF, meeting monthly, with an open membership. The core membership makes active contributions to OTPF, in running the sessions and in presenting lightning talks, as well as using contacts to organise lightning talks. Towards the end

of the final project year, it is envisioned that these two levels will begin to merge, with the work package meetings phasing out and organically shifting to the OTPF meetings where discussion and collaboration will continue.

The OTPF remains a relatively new platform. In the past year, OTPF has focused on establishing regular attendance amongst its members, as well as shaping a standard agenda that reflects the community's needs and interests. The members voted to hold meetings monthly, with the frequency to be reviewed over time. The meetings consist of a monthly newsbulletin of TRE news items, event and workshop announcements, and other related updates, followed by one to two lightning talks per meeting. The meetings then hold a community Q&A session, and the format of these is still being reviewed, with members able to submit questions for discussion.

The meetings averaged around 10 participants per meeting, with higher numbers in the very first meeting in April 2025 and the post-summer meeting in September 2025. The meetings have had presentations on topics such as SATRE, the 2nd year EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, EOSC Finland node, and on TREs run by SWITCH in Switzerland and BIH Charité in Germany. The meetings also include key news from related initiatives, such as the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and Data and Analytics Research Environments UK (DARE UK).

The OTPF will continue to develop as a forum for TRE related community discussion and information sharing, building on the foundational work of establishing the Provider Forum in the first project year, and focusing on expanding the membership and creating platforms of information gathering and exchange. Currently the OTPF only has members from European countries, but it aims to be open and inclusive, and it is expected that the membership may grow beyond Europe in the future. One indication of this is that the second TRE survey had one respondent from the United States, indicating that WP11's dissemination efforts have reached outside Europe already.

The long-term potential contribution of OTPF is to act as a community-sustained platform for TRE providers that boosts alignment across the TRE landscape, fosters collaborations, and facilitates the exchange of ideas and knowledge. The OTPF should seek to align itself with EOSC developments, with its relationship with the EOSC Federation yet to be determined. However, it is likely that in the future members of the OTPF will have TREs onboarded to different EOSC nodes (depending on what EOSC node their TRE is best aligned with). The OTPF may thereby anticipate having connections to several different nodes in the future. In this scenario, open discussion on how TREs have integrated in the EOSC Federation is vital, to share information and experiences of onboarding and reducing duplication of work. The OTPF is ideally suited to support this discussion.

4.4 Facilitating adoption of the Blueprint and developed technologies

In the context of EOSC-ENTRUST, the adoption of its outputs can be defined in several ways. These are: 1) adoption as direct use, meaning that the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint/developed technologies have been implemented by a TRE service provider for their environment; 2) adoption as adaptation, meaning that the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint/developed technologies have been altered by a TRE service provider to suit their specific environment; 3) adoption as influence, meaning that the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint/developed technologies have influenced a TRE provider to develop their environment further.

To assess the levels of adoption amongst work package members, WP11 conducted information gathering in late 2025 to check the status of adoption across all partners. 11 out of the 17 partners provided this information, with one partner outlining adoption for two TREs, bringing the total of TREs consulted to 12. Their responses outlined the extent of their adoption as well as outlining their key challenges in this. The adoption was for the most part based on the Year 1 version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, as the Year 2 version had only just been published, with the result that most WP11 partners had not yet had sufficient time to react to this.

4.4.1 Blueprint adoption across providers

Based on the data provided by WP11 providers, the adoption of the first version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint across providers is characterised by a “multi-speed” landscape, where established providers are mapping existing systems to the framework while newer or national-scale providers are using it as a transition roadmap.

12 providers / services responded to the questionnaire. Of these, 5 are in the “1) adoption as direct use” or in the “2) adoption as adaptation” category. They have already fully or partially adopted the Year 1 Blueprint, with some of these early adopters also beginning to integrate guidelines from the Year 2 version despite it not having been publicly published at the time of consultation. Conversely, 7 providers are in the “3) adoption as influence” category and have not yet adopted the Blueprint as they are currently in the phase of evaluating or reviewing the framework to determine its alignment with their existing infrastructures. This split highlights a transition in the community, where 5 of respondents are actively implementing the framework, while the remaining 7 are using the Blueprint primarily as a strategic reference for future architectural and policy alignment.

The adoption of the Blueprint varies considerably depending on the maturity of each partner’s infrastructure. Established TREs such as Sigma2 (NORTRE) and anDREa (used by Health-RI and others) have been able to integrate the Blueprint effectively by mapping it onto their existing architectures and well-defined security frameworks, including the Five Safes and SATRE, thereby meeting the Blueprint’s functional requirements with minimal disruption. Partners in a prototyping or transition phase show a different pattern: BSC is using the Blueprint primarily as a guiding reference while developing a new system, whereas CSC reports that adoption is largely straightforward, requiring only minor adjustments to current practices. Finally, several partners remain in an evaluation phase, with organisations such as GRNET (ARIS/HARMONI), the University of Ljubljana, and Uppsala University actively reviewing the Blueprint to assess its alignment with their existing workflows, but without full implementation at this stage.

Based on the detailed feedback from WP11, the following table summarises the adoption status, activities, and specific stances of the participating organisations as of early 2026.

Provider	Current Adoption Status	Key Adoption Activities
BSC	Prototyping	BSC-TRE uses the Blueprint as an architectural and policy reference. Work is ongoing to align the Blueprint with in-production HPC systems.

Provider	Current Adoption Status	Key Adoption Activities
CSC	Adoption	Integrating the Blueprint into CSC Node services; reports that adoption requires only minor workflow adjustments. The main problem is the legal part.
GRNET (ARIS/HARMONI)	Review/Strategic Guidance	They have not yet adopted the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint at this stage; adoption here would mean using it as an architectural and policy reference and as a benchmarking tool to assess the maturity of data archiving (HARMONI) and HPC security (ARIS). For HPC, they are currently reviewing its components to understand alignment with existing security, data-governance, and access-control workflows. This involves using the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint as architectural guidance to evaluate how its patterns fit the current HPC environment.
Sigma2 (NORTRE: TSD/SAFE/HUNT Cloud)	Aligned	Acting as a mature reference; mapping existing RAZ/SDZ architectures to the Blueprint to enhance external federation readiness. They have worked with both Year 1 and Year 2 Blueprints. Their architecture aligns closely with the functional requirements of a TRE component in the Blueprint (specifically, the Research Analytics Zones (RAZs) and Secure Data Zones (SDZs))
University of Ljubljana	Review/Strategic Guidance	Benchmarking local services against the Blueprint while awaiting national legislation to enable full technical deployment. Adoption for them means (1) legal/policy alignment requiring wider national/EU consensus and (2) technical deployment in their TRE aligned with local technologies and interoperability needs.
Uppsala University	Pending	No. Adoption would mean ensuring compliance with EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint requirements regarding policy and process, as well as technical implementational changes to allow federated access. This poses two quite disparate challenges and becomes something of a catch-22.

Provider	Current Adoption Status	Key Adoption Activities
Bielefeld University (de.NBI Cloud)	Active Adoption	de.NBI Cloud has evaluated the Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and has performed a mapping exercise for two of the SPEs they currently have in development, where they have adopted common terminology for actors, processes and systems in the systems' architecture. They are adopting specific building blocks from the Blueprints. They plan to publish the results as a white paper in Q1 2026. They will only be able to review and adopt the Year 2 Blueprint later in 2026.
LNDS	Active Adoption	Ongoing modifications to SPE infrastructure to ensure technical interoperability and policy alignment with the reference architecture.
MyDRE(anDREa)	Active Adoption , financially viable, serves multiple institutes, including Health-RI.	Performed comprehensive SATRE self-assessments (scoring 9.0+). Adoption also means ensuring their documented controls (e.g., A.05.31 Legal requirements, A.8.13 Information backup) to satisfy the specific interoperability constraints introduced in the Blueprint. ISO 27001:2023 certified. Used by PhDs up to international multi-center studies; several H2020.
IT4I@VSB – Technical University of Ostrava	Evaluation Phase	They have not adapted the Blueprint. They are currently evaluating Blueprint alignment for HPC; engaging with EuroHPC Federation to address Czech national identity/AAI gaps.
Sciensano	On-hold	Organisational (at the national level). The Minister of Public Health has decided to integrate Sciensano's Healthdata.be platform into the Belgian Health Data Agency (HDA). This merger is part of a broader effort to centralise health data in preparation for the European Health Data Space (EHDS). The transition has led to delays and a standstill in several initiatives.

Table 3. EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint adoption levels by TRE provider.

4.4.2 Identified barriers to adoption

The barriers to adopting the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint can be categorised into four distinct dimensions of interoperability: Technical, Legal, Organizational, and Financial.

Technically, there is a significant gap in aligning “Five Safes” principles with shared HPC clusters – specifically regarding project-level isolation in batch-scheduling environments – as well as a lack of clear compliance guidance for cloud-native TREs using hyperscaler tools.

Legal and regulatory uncertainty is a second major hurdle. Many partners face conflicting requirements, as fragmented national regulations create significant administrative burden for cross-border collaboration. Local compliance rules often conflict with federation goals, driven by differing national interpretations of GDPR and the evolving EHDS, as well as unresolved issues around liability and intellectual property in federated settings.

Organisational and structural barriers prevent many willing partners from moving beyond evaluation. Several national providers report a “mandate deficit,” lacking formal legislative authority to align their missions with the EOSC-ENTRUST framework. Others are stalled by national agency reorganisations, such as Sciensano’s merger into the Belgian Health Data Agency. These transitions temporarily halt adoption efforts. In the absence of clear Rules of Participation and standardised Connector Kits, many organisations remain technically ready but legally and organisationally constrained.

Recently, questions of digital sovereignty have become a key discussion point that also impacts progress. This has an impact on discussions surrounding TREs, especially from the perspective of cross-border collaboration. The uncertainty hits every aspect, from EU-policy making to committing to invest in TRE/SPE solutions, and as EOSC-ENTRUST evolves and partners explore Blueprint adoption, new barriers may emerge as organisations respond to data sovereignty needs.

Finally, financial concerns center on the high costs of achieving “federation readiness” and meeting rigorous standards like ISO 27001 without the security of long-term funding under future EU financial frameworks.

The identified barriers can be summarised as shown by the following table:

Provider	Identified Barriers to Adoption
BSC	Technical alignment of Blueprint architecture with production HPC systems; specifically project-level isolation and federated AAI.
CSC	Legal vagueness regarding data types and EHDS impact; pain points in accounting and cross-border regulatory compliance.
GRNET	Lack of national/high-level policy mandates for full implementation; difficulty aligning HPC policies across non-health research domains.
Bielefeld (de.NBI)	Technical challenges in “user-operated” SPE models; need for additional national funding and guided technical certification. Different scopes and requirements of academic vs commercial TRE operators.
Sigma2 (NORTRE)	Harmonisation of diverse national legal and technical systems into a single scalable European framework; federation readiness.

Provider	Identified Barriers to Adoption
Health-RI (anDREa)	Fragmentation of national regulations; lack of guidance for Cloud-native TREs vs on-premise assumptions; integration overhead for EOSC AAI; no mature and maintained governance framework and rules of engagement; public money funding competing existing services.
University of Ljubljana	Lack of formal national mandate/enabling legislation; balancing EuroHPC integration with EHDS alignment.
Uppsala University	Organisational “catch-22” between technical readiness for federated access and a lack of national steering mandate.
Sciensano	National-level organisational shifts and delays due to integration into the new Belgian Health Data Agency (HDA).
LNDS	Maintaining service continuity while adapting existing infrastructure; legal uncertainties regarding cross-border data sharing, particularly regarding EHDS implementation timeline and requirements; clearer view on how national HDAB requirements map to EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint components.
IT4I	Interoperability between identity systems and access control; aligning national legal/technical frameworks with HPC infrastructures.

Table 4. Summary of Provider-Specific Barriers to Adoption

4.5 Planning an overall approach for making TREs part of the EOSC services

4.5.1 Approaches for EOSC integration

The discussions in WP11, including the EOSC-ENTRUST sustainability seminar held in November 2025, converge on the view that TREs are a core instrument for implementing EU policy priorities around data sovereignty, secure AI-driven research, and ethical access to sensitive data within EOSC. Providers broadly agree that TREs should not be treated as isolated national solutions, but as composable services that can be integrated into the EOSC Federation through multiple pathways. At the same time, especially in the EHDS setting, there is a strong lobby for national only solutions, or at least that a few specific existing solutions only qualify. EOSC nodes will have to make a strong value proposition for the benefits that TRE providers gain from being part of the federated node ecosystem. To this end, the pathways to integration must be clearly planned.

WP11 consulted the project’s TRE providers on how they envision integration to EOSC to occur. Three main integration approaches emerge from this partner feedback. First, several public providers envisage their TRE or SPE becoming part of EOSC via national or thematic nodes, where the TRE forms a key component of the node’s service portfolio. This model allows for highly optimised needs of a specific domain. Second, some actors (especially commercial or mixed public-private platforms) focus on domain independent solutions; generic like myDRE (anDREa) or specialised like Multi Party Computation of Rosemanlabs¹⁸ that can and are used in collaboration by users. These actors see

¹⁸ Rosemanlabs: <https://rosemanlabs.com/en/>

themselves primarily as EOSC-listed services rather than nodes, with clear accreditation and auditing mechanisms to ensure compliance with EOSC-ENTRUST and EOSC requirements. Third, federations such as NORTRE demonstrate how a group of national TREs can act collectively as a “federated provider” that interfaces with EOSC as a single, coordinated entity.

Each of the integration approaches has its pros and cons. Given the size, diversity and evolving needs of the TRE ecosystem, we may expect that there will be multiple pathways to EOSC integration, rather than a singular solution that fits all use cases. To this end, TRE providers also require clear information from EOSC that makes it simpler to understand the differences between integration approaches, enabling TRE providers to make fast but well-informed decisions.

A recurring theme in integration is the distinction between the TRE inventory and the TRE provider catalogue. The inventory, maintained by the Provider Forum and updated by WP11, offers a landscape overview for providers and funders, whereas the catalogue is envisaged as part of the EOSC offering, with more detailed technical and service-level information. WP11 partners also point to the option of defining an EOSC “TRE provider profile” within the existing EOSC provider catalogue, so that TRE-specific requirements can be expressed as a specialisation of the general EOSC profiles.

4.5.2 Recommendations for EOSC integration

Based on the current status of adoption and EOSC-readiness, WP11 recommends that TRE integration into EOSC should follow a layered approach, including both policy and governance level approaches, as well as technical approaches.

At the policy and governance level, EOSC should recognise 1) TREs, 2) TREs that also support federation, and 3) TRE federations (such as NORTRE) as first-class actors in the EOSC Federation, with clearly defined roles, responsibilities and “rules of participation” that reflect the additional obligations associated with sensitive data processing. EOSC should develop a policy that has considered the spectrum of TREs and their federation capabilities, thereby enabling EOSC integration.

At the technical level, EOSC should support a TRE-specific provider profile in its catalogue and federation specifications, including explicit requirements for AAI interoperability, audit logging, security baselines, and data-use governance aligned with the Five Safes and emerging EHDS -implementing act on SPEs. The TRE provider catalogue and the TRE inventory can and should both be used to support such a profile being developed.

Furthermore, it is important that EOSC integration pathways are compatible with existing and emerging national federations of TREs. For NORTRE and similar initiatives, this implies that EOSC must allow a federated “provider of providers” model, where multiple national TREs can be represented under a shared governance framework while still retaining local legal responsibilities and operational autonomy. NORTRE currently represents this model as a group of TREs from within one member state. The Open TRE Provider Forum, whose sustainability planning is led by Sigma2 in WP12, is well placed to act as a community vehicle for developing and validating such models.

Finally, EOSC integration should be tightly coupled to the requirements management framework described above. In practice, this means using the updated TRE inventory, adoption data and gap analyses as evidence to refine EOSC’s federation specifications for TREs, prioritise interoperability investments where appropriate (e.g. connector kits, reference implementations), and align with related European initiatives such as EuroHPC and EHDS.

4.6 Supporting providers to onboard TREs to EOSC

4.6.1 Support required for EOSC onboarding

WP11 feedback highlights that, for most providers, the key bottleneck is not willingness to onboard to EOSC but the lack of clear, end-to-end support for doing so. Providers require practical guidance on how TREs can satisfy EOSC's federation specifications in the context of sensitive data, particularly for AAI integration, service registration and cataloguing, logging and monitoring interfaces, and alignment with EOSC security and data-use policies. The most pressing barrier is the lack of a concise technical framework and onboarding process, which may also be explained by these still being developed within the EOSC Federation itself. The onboarding of a TRE onto an EOSC node may also contain a formal certification and accreditation process as a prerequisite to becoming an accredited TRE. Two facets are thereby required: first, and most pressingly, the technical process must be solved to enable integration. Once this has been addressed, TRE accreditation through a certifiable framework that independent auditors can verify can commence.

Legal and contractual support is also seen as essential. Providers operating national TREs have to reconcile EOSC participation with national legislation, sector-specific regulations (e.g. health data laws), and institutional risk frameworks. They therefore call for template contractual clauses, model data-processing agreements, and guidance on liability allocation in federated TRE scenarios. Many partners explicitly state that clarity on these issues is a precondition for onboarding.

In addition, there is a strong demand for training and capacity building tailored to different provider types: national public TREs, HPC-attached TREs, cloud-native TRE platforms, and mixed public-private services. Providers emphasise that onboarding support should go beyond generic EOSC training and include concrete technical examples (reference architectures, connector kits) and domain-specific workflows for sensitive data processing. The EOSC Federation is currently working on onboarding requirements and testing the nodes through use cases; one should focus on the TRE question specifically to provide an example for other TRE providers. This is especially important as, even with NIS2, while an EU directive, there is no single body identified that takes upon itself to provide necessary training and support.

4.6.2 Recommendations for onboarding support

In light of these needs for onboarding support, WP11 recommends that EOSC and the EOSC-ENTRUST consortium jointly develop a structured onboarding pathway for TREs. This pathway should combine: (1) a TRE-specific onboarding guide that explains how to meet EOSC Federation requirements; (2) technical reference implementations for common integration scenarios (e.g. connecting TRE AAI to EOSC AAI, exposing TRE services in the catalogue, integrating audit logs with central monitoring); and (3) a set of legal and policy templates that providers and national authorities can adapt. These support acts would benefit from a TRE-focused use case, which could contribute to their development.

In light of these needs, WP11 recommends EOSC and the EOSC-ENTRUST consortium to jointly develop a governance and rules of engagement framework using ISO. The foundation should either be ISO 27001 and NIS2 or should be mapped against ISO 27001 and NIS2. ISO ensures proper procedures and has an 'infrastructure' to include, via national bodies, the interests of all stakeholders.

Sigma2 and the NORTRE federation can contribute to this work by using their own onboarding journey as a concrete use case, documenting the steps, decisions and compromises involved in preparing Norwegian TREs for EOSC participation. The same applies to partners who are aligning HPC-centric or cloud-native environments with the Blueprint: their experiences can be turned into reusable onboarding patterns for other providers.

Support is also needed in identifying the pathway for TREs, either individually or as a federation, to integrate with the node-framework of EOSC. At the time of writing, 13 pilot nodes and the EOSC EU Node, form the EOSC nodes, with the pilot nodes consisting of national nodes, thematic nodes, and infrastructure nodes. None of these nodes are yet ready to service sensitive data, although solutions to this will become more timely as the EOSC Federation matures. Currently there is no clear process for TRE onboarding onto nodes, or guidance for TRE accreditation to be considered suitable for onboarding. TREs may approach a national node in the country they are based in, or they may consider a thematic node, e.g. the Life Sciences Connect node, as suitable. Even in this scenario, onboarding requirements are not yet defined, and the nodes do not have the capacity to handle sensitive data. To this end, a use case focused on testing a TRE onboarding is needed.

Finally, the OTPF should be leveraged as a community backbone for onboarding support. As envisaged in the WP12 plans, OTPF can host regular clinics, share checklists and best practices, and act as a channel for collecting provider feedback on EOSC onboarding processes over time. Embedding onboarding support within this community structure will help ensure that the EOSC-ENTRUST results remain sustainable and that new TREs can join the European network beyond the lifetime of the project.

5. Results

The key results of WP11 include the updated TRE inventory, the development of the requirements management framework, the launch of the Open TRE Provider Forum (OTPF), and producing the Blueprint adoption analysis as well as providing initial findings to support strategy development for EOSC integration.

- 1. Updated TRE Inventory:** The revised TRE inventory is a key achievement for WP11, as this updated format aligned the inventory with the TRE catalogue. The inventory expanded the scope of TREs captured, providing a broader set of data than its first iteration. The updated inventory will further support Blueprint development and the final version of the TRE catalogue.
- 2. Requirements Management framework:** WP11 developed and validated the Requirements Management Plan (RMP). The framework was applied to the MS8 Driver-derived requirements, resulting in their registration as baseline in the EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Repository. The framework included the definition and implementation of interoperable and machine-readable requirements definitions, a Requirement Adoption Traceability Matrix (RATM), and supporting evidence and assessment models. After dedicated workshops to gather feedback and test the framework, an edited version of the framework was produced. This work demonstrated how heterogeneous and high-level requirements can be operationalised in a consistent and provider-agnostic manner, while preserving their original intent. The framework provides a methodological basis for Blueprint adoption analysis,

EOSC-readiness assessment, and future refinement of TRE requirements, and constitutes a reusable asset for the OTPF and related EOSC initiatives.

3. **Open TRE Provider Forum:** The OTPF holds a central place for the EOSC-ENTRUST project, being the first pan-European effort to create a platform for TRE service providers. The forum seeks to foster information sharing, collaboration, and alignment on TRE developments. The OTPF meets monthly, additionally to the biweekly WP11 meetings that remain closed to project partners. At the end of January 2026, OTPF had 42 individuals on the membership list, representing 27 different TRE service providers.
4. **EOSC-readiness and gap analysis:** WP11 has produced initial findings on EOSC-readiness in the rapidly changing EOSC landscape. The EOSC Portal, as described in the grant proposal, has been replaced by new EOSC structures, and the federated node model officially launched in November 2025. As such, the findings on EOSC-readiness are mixed as there remain ambiguities on what this means for TREs. The report offers recommendations on how TREs can strategise to integrate into the EOSC ecosystem as it currently stands, with changes expected before the end of the project.
5. **Workshops and training:** WP11 contributed to EOSC-ENTRUST workshops, both in-person and online, sharing the outputs and findings thus far, and contributing to the work of other work packages. These include the second Requirements and Capabilities workshop¹⁹, the second Evaluation and Adoption workshop²⁰, the Sustainability workshop, and the Blueprint validation workshop. WP11 partners have also contributed to training packages through interviews.

6. Conclusions

During the second year of EOSC-ENTRUST, WP11 focused on supporting the evolving landscape of TREs through community building and information gathering. The work conducted between M13–M24 has advanced the project’s objectives by strengthening the understanding of TRE capabilities, clarifying requirements, fostering TRE provider collaboration, and analysing levels of adoption and pathways for TRE integration in the EOSC Federation.

A key achievement has been the publication of the updated TRE inventory (MS11). By expanding the number of TREs included and aligning its structure with the TRE catalogue, the updated inventory serves as a shared reference point for TRE capabilities, common practices, and major gaps across Europe. It also provides input for other EOSC-ENTRUST work packages, particularly those developing the Blueprint and the TRE catalogue. The findings confirm that while TREs share maturity in areas such as security, project isolation, and data types and tooling, notable challenges remain, including limited federation readiness, and diverse policy and governance models. EOSC-ENTRUST is

¹⁹ Kirschenmann, S., Winge, I., Sætrom, P., Kallberg, M., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., Lehväslaiho, H., van der Kant, A., Laine, H., Lényi, P., Liampotis, N., Gonzalo Jimenez, E., Fernández González, J. M., Couldridge, J., & Quinlan, P. (2025). 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop.. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15473397>

²⁰ Sætrom, P., Maccallum, P., van der Kant, A., Vihervalli, U., Kuba, M., Lehväslaiho, H., Cole, C., Kallberg, M., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., Winge, I., Kirschenmann, S., Couldridge, J., Fernández González, J. M., Codó, L., Iborra de Toledo, P., & Nagaraja Grellscheid, S. (2025). MS18 - Second EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation & Adoption Workshop. Second Evaluation and adoption Workshop, Bergen, Norway.. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17160733>

well-poised to address the challenges of technical interoperability and requirement frameworks, but many challenges are at policy level and will require work outside the confines of the project.

The development of the requirements management framework marks another important milestone. The Requirements Management Plan defines a structured and standards-aligned approach, covering the full requirements lifecycle from stakeholder elicitation through analysis, traceability, and evaluation. By introducing a systematic, evidence-oriented mechanism for interpreting, validating, and tracing requirements, WP11 has introduced a methodological foundation for TRE evaluation. In particular, the Requirement Adoption Traceability Matrix provides a practical instrument for linking abstract, Driver-derived requirements to verifiable capabilities and supporting artefacts. This framework is presented here as a methodological reference model; other work packages are invited to reuse, extend, and operationalise it in their respective activities.

The launch and growth of the OTPF will support WP11/12's ongoing work, especially for the project's sustainability. The OTPF has established itself as the first open, European community forum for TRE service providers, reaching over 40 members in its first year. By convening regular meetings, enabling knowledge exchange, and creating a channel for community-driven alignment, the OTPF addresses fragmentation in practices and interoperability, as well as creates a space for collaboration. The participation of members outside of EOSC-ENTRUST showcases a need in the TRE landscape for such a forum, positing the OTPF well for the final project year when it strives for longevity.

WP11 has also completed an analysis of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint adoption within the project. Findings show a layered adoption landscape, with some providers already mapping or integrating the Blueprint components, and others using it as a strategic point of reference. The barriers identified to adoption include legal challenges nationally, technical constraints, organisational transitions, and uncertainties linked to data sovereignty and EU-level legislation. There is quite significant work in this area, therefore, and in the final project year WP12 has to strategically engage with and address these barriers.

Finally, WP11 has provided an initial assessment of EOSC-readiness and outlined pathways for TRE integration into the EOSC Federation. The EOSC Federation model has emerged during the lifespan of EOSC-ENTRUST, and as such the project has had to adjust to the new node-based federation approach. Although EOSC nodes currently lack capabilities for processing sensitive data, WP11's work highlights feasible integration approaches, emphasising the need for TRE-specific onboarding processes, clear policy guidance, and a differentiated model that recognises both individual TREs and TRE federations. One of the most direct and impactful ways to push work forward in this area would be for a TRE integration use case to be conducted, to lay the groundwork for further TREs to modify and learn from. These recommendations will inform the project's contributions to EOSC and will support TRE providers preparing for future onboarding, while also emphasising that more clarity on procedures are needed from EOSC.

Overall, the work completed in M13–M24 sets WP11 well for the final project year. WP11 has improved the visibility, comparability, and collective organisation of the European TRE landscape, clarified practical and conceptual pathways toward EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint adoption, and analysed the different scenarios for TREs to become part of EOSC offerings, highlighting the gaps that still exist before this becomes achievable. Building on this work, in the final year of the project as WP12, the

work package will focus on sustainability, further adoption analysis, a more extensive and final TRE inventory, with the overall aim of consolidating the position of OTPF within the European TRE landscape.

7. Next steps

As EOSC-ENTRUST begins its final project year, WP11 partners will commence work on WP12 tasks. The main focus of WP12 will be supporting the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint through adoption, developing approaches to EOSC integration, expanding the TRE provider network and planning for its sustainability beyond the end of the project. Key objectives include expanding the number of TREs that demonstrate EOSC-readiness – within the current understanding of what that entails – and maintaining an updated overview of the TRE landscape through updating the TRE inventory. Furthermore, WP12 will analyse the adoption of EOSC-ENTRUST outputs more extensively and produce a sustainability model for the Open TRE Provider Forum.

The first focus will be in updating the TRE survey and running this for a third and final time in May and June 2026, which will produce a final version of the TRE inventory to facilitate continued requirement building. This will involve all WP12 participants and will be coordinated by CSC. The objective is to capture as many of the TREs currently in the inventory as possible, to ensure their capabilities are captured and categorised comprehensively, with any remaining gaps addressed. Cross-WP alignment will be ensured before the survey is published, especially with WP9 and WP15. The final inventory will address EOSC-readiness in alignment with the current document, providing a final update on requirements also for the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. The task will address relevant adoption barriers identified in this document, evaluating these based on a final round of stakeholder engagement. WP12 aims to make use of contacts in the OTPF for dissemination to increase the number of TREs captured in the final inventory. Preliminary outcomes will be presented in the final Requirements and Capabilities Workshop. The task will also work towards supporting the EOSC integration of TREs, increasing the number of TREs listed in the inventory and, subsequently, the TRE catalogue.

A second focus will be the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint adoption level assessment. This task will be led by DeIC, with contribution from all members. The task will gather up-to-date information on adoption of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint amongst TRE service providers, capturing also national perspectives, which will be presented in *D12.1 – Final report on adoption and sustainability, including EOSC & National perspectives*. The task will document benefits achieved through adoption and discuss potential future adoption cases at institutional and national levels and in the current EOSC context. The task will further examine barriers to adoption, especially at national levels, and identify strategies to overcome these. The findings will be presented at the final Evaluation and Adoption Workshop, outlining strategies for increased adoption.

Related to these efforts is the sustained growth of the OTPF and putting together a sustainability model. This activity will be led by Sigma2, with contributions from all partners. The sustainability model will identify options for continuing the OTPF's activities, aligning this with the current EOSC landscape. The model will include onboarding strategies for new TRE providers for new adoption cases, and will be presented in the final Evaluation and Adoption Workshop. The challenge here will be to identify a governance model for OTPF as it transitions to an in-kind contribution forum of TRE experts.

Lastly, WP12 will collaborate across the project in the final year. Stakeholder engagement will be particularly important for the expansion of the TRE inventory and OTPF membership. Dissemination of outputs thus far remains key, especially for the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, as adoption levels continue to be assessed.

8. Impact

A key impact of WP11 has been the launch of the Open TRE Provider Forum (OTPF) as an additional platform of exchange and collaboration. When the EOSC-ENTRUST project concludes at M36, the aim is that the OTPF will continue, and as such the Providers Forum will continue to meet and collaborate while the biweekly meetings of WP12 phase out. There is still work to be done to meet this goal, with a sustainability model to be drafted, but these efforts to bring together TRE service providers has already had a positive impact. The OTPF has helped TRE service providers to form channels of communication, raise awareness and improve understanding of TREs across Europe, and helped build communities around TREs. All of these will be important as work on TRE interoperability and federation continues.

The public and updated TRE inventory has also been a major contribution. A pervasive challenge for TREs has been a lack of information about the TRE landscape, and the updated inventory seeks to address this. By providing a public record of different TREs and listing their capabilities, WP11 has contributed towards an enhanced understanding of TRE functionalities, commonalities, and challenges in the existing landscape. This information has supported many EOSC-ENTRUST outputs from other work packages.

This report further has provided a discussion of current adoption levels of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and highlighted barriers to adoption. The ways in which the Blueprint has been adopted in the current sample shows varied approaches, and it is clear that significant challenges still remain. This can inform the project's final year, so that WP12 as well as other work packages can take these barriers into account and seek to overcome them. This analysis further informs other stakeholders, such as policymakers, on issues arising from TRE interoperability and standardisation efforts, providing a good understanding of what changes are needed to make these processes easier.

Lastly, this report serves the EOSC Federation, including the EOSC Tripartite Governance and EOSC members. As the EOSC Federation evolves, there is a growing need for TREs to become a part of services offered by EOSC nodes. This report has highlighted the possible pathways through which this can be realised, along with recommendations on what support is needed and what requires further clarification and guidance. This discussion will impact progress done on this in the coming years, and especially may be of benefit to nodes who are in discussions about onboarding TREs.